

The Role of Community Care Groups in Supporting Community Client Empowerment in the Community

Doris Rahmat¹, Waluyo Slamet Pradoto²

^{1,2}Law Faculty Universitas Slamet Riyadi Surakarta

ABSTRACT: Pancasila is the thought that the function of punishment is no longer just a deterrent, but also an effort to rehabilitate and reintegrate the social inmates of prisons. Prisons have an important role in the justice system. There are 4 main functions of the Penitentiary, namely; 1) Guidance; 2) Assistance 3) Supervision, and 4) Community Research. The existence of the Correctional Care Community Group (Pokmas Lipas) is very important in supporting the empowerment of correctional clients in the community, Pokmas have their respective roles to support the reintegration of correctional clients so that they can return to the community. The implementation of the correctional system which is the implementation of Pancasila values, namely coaching the personality of prisoners, is carried out by a coaching program with forms of coaching in the form of religious education, general education, skills courses, recreation, sports, arts and job training.

KEYWORDS: Correctional, Group, Role.

A. INTRODUCTION

The Indonesian state is based on Pancasila, a nation that highly upholds human rights without exception in the development of prisoners. Pancasila are thoughts that the function of punishment is no longer just a deterrent, but is also an effort to rehabilitate and reintegrate socially inmates in prison.

Crime is an act or an act that violates the law and moral values that exist in society. Crimes have a nature that is detrimental to society and are carried out by members of the community as well, the government through law enforcement officers tries to overcome the disturbances of these crimes. The countermeasures are carried out in two ways, namely through preventive measures and repressive measures. (Erina et al: 1266).

Correctional Center (BAPAS) is a correctional technical implementation unit that functions to provide guidance to correctional clients. In addition to carrying out the supervisory function, the prison has an important role in the judicial system. There are 4 main functions of the Correctional Center, namely; 1) Guidance; 2) Assistance 3) Supervision, and 4) Community Research conducted by Community Counselors (PK). (Adrian Sofyan, 814, 2020).

Most prisoners who inhabit correctional institutions lack an adequate background of religious education, both formal education and education planted in the family environment, in the development of the times this is mostly carried out by people who are highly educated and people who are very knowledgeable about religion, overall this is the main basis that causes them to violate the law, namely the different levels of faith and piety, prisoners require intensive and directed religious guidance. Religious development has a dual function, in addition to fulfilling obligations as religious people, as well as therapy to form a personality that is in accordance with the norms of religious life and society. (Dwidja Priyatno, 2006: 152) The social system as stipulated in Article 2 of Law Number 22 Year 2022 is implemented to:

- a. Provide guarantees of protection for prisoners and children
- b. Improving the quality of personality and independence of inmates so that they are aware of their mistakes, improve themselves, and do not repeat criminal acts, so that they can be accepted back by a good environment, obey the law, are responsible, and can play an active role in development.
- c. provide protection to the public from the repetition of criminal acts.

Realizing this, Indonesia's social system has long emphasized on the aspect of fostering prisoners, correctional students or correctional clients who have preventive, curative, rehabilitative, and educative characteristics. Although the penitentiary system has been implemented so far, various legal instruments that formally underlie it still originate from the Dutch East Indies which is a system of imprisonment, therefore the practice of correctional has been carried out by new ideas contained in Pancasila.

In the correctional system, prisoners, correctional students are entitled to spiritual and physical guidance, and their rights are guaranteed to carry out worship, to communicate with outside parties, both family and other parties, and to obtain information both in print and electronic media, to obtain proper education and etc., to implement the correctional system, it is also necessary to have the participation of the community both in cooperating in conducting coaching and with the nature of being willing to accept back prisoners who have finished serving their sentences.

B. RESEARCH QUESTION

What is the role of community groups who care about correctional facilities in supporting the empowerment of correctional clients in the community?

C. DISCUSSION

Since 1964 the development system for prisoners and criminal children has changed fundamentally, namely from a prison system to a social system. The social system is a series of criminal law enforcement unit, therefore its implementation cannot be separated from the development of a general concept of punishment.

Convicts are not objects but subjects who are no different from other humans, who at any time can make mistakes or mistakes that can be subject to punishment, so that they do not need to be eradicated, but factors that can be criminalized. Correctional institutions as the spearhead of the implementation of protection are places to achieve these goals through education, rehabilitation and reintegration. In line with the role of the penitentiary, it is appropriate that the correctional officer who carries out the task of fostering and securing the inmates, in this law is designated as a functional official of law enforcement. In general, the development of independence must be improved through a skills development approach, including restoration of self-esteem as individuals and as citizens who believe they still have productive potential for nation building and therefore they are also educated to master certain skills in order to live independently and be useful for development. (Muhammad Ali Equatora, 2018 :20-26)

The Community Care Group (POKMAS LIMAS) is a group of work partners who have high attention and are willing to participate in the administration of correctional facilities in order to support Correctional Inmates in the process of social reintegration. Elements of the community who are members of POKMAS must be active and creative in creating various activities and be able to provide benefits to related parties by increasing the role of government and organizations, changing lawbreakers into individuals who are more socially and economically independent and become useful members of the community. (Adrian Sofyan, 818, 2020) Guidance that will be provided by community groups to Correctional Clients so that they can develop their potential and obtain benefits for correctional clients.

The existence Pokmas Lipas is an innovation from the Directorate General of Corrections to improve the duties and functions of the Correctional Center (Bapas). Fathers are correctional technical implementing units whose function is to provide guidance to correctional clients. To improve the duties and functions of correctional institutions, especially those related to guiding correctional clients, collaborate with several Pokmas Lipas in the local area (Dimas Gilang Setyawan, Ali Muhammad, 281, 2021)

The problem of time in terms of fostering prisoners is an important thing, considering that the process of fostering prisoners must go through systematic stages of coaching, before finally being released back into the community, but in fact in some cases, convicts who have been sentenced to light criminal punishments return to committing crimes. a new crime, which causes the person to deal with the law and return to the prison (Made et al, 452, 2022). To achieve a good coaching system, participation does not only come from officers, but also from the community in addition to the correctional client itself, in an effort to provide participation, a correctional officer always acts in accordance with the principles of correctional. A correctional officer can only be considered participating if he is able to show attitudes, actions and wisdom in reflecting protection for both the community and prisoners. Implementation is a policy which is basically a change or transformation that is multi-organizational, that is, changes implemented through this policy implementation strategy are related to various levels of society (Made dkk, 453,2022)

D. CONCLUSION

The existence of the Correctional Care Community Group (Pokmas Lipas) is very important in supporting the empowerment of correctional clients in the community, Pokmas have their respective roles to support the reintegration of correctional clients so that they can return to the community. the implementation of the correctional system which is the

implementation of Pancasila values, namely coaching the personality of prisoners, is carried out by a coaching program with forms of coaching in the form of religious education, general education, skills courses, recreation, sports, arts and job training. The empowerment of correctional clients must be supported by all parties, especially community groups so that correctional clients can later return to the community and participate in their daily environment.

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